

INVESTIGATION ON VISCOSITY OF EMULSIONS

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Viscosities of xylene emulsions stabilised with sodium oleate, myristate, laurate, capriate and saponin have been measured in a rotary viscometer. The viscosities depend a great deal on the nature of the emulsifier used. Different viscosity equations have been tested and Richardson's equation with a slight modification has been found to fit the experimental data best.

In a previous communication (this *Journal*, 1952, 23, 573) viscosities of emulsions stabilised with cetyldimethylbenzylammonium chloride, cetylpyridinium bromide, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide and magnesium oleate have been recorded. It has been shown therein that of all the viscosity equations, those of Sibree and Richardson fit the experimental data best. Viscosity of xylene emulsions made with a few other soaps e.g., sodium oleate, myristate, laurate, capriate and saponin are recorded in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

The arrangement for the measurement of viscosity and temperature control has been described in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*). Sodium oleate has been prepared by the method of Berkman (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1935, 33, 528). Oleic acid was converted into barium oleate and dissolved in ether. The ethereal solution was decomposed by HCl, oleic acid extracted with ether and dried over Na_2SO_4 . Ether was evaporated off and oleic acid distilled at a reduced pressure. To the pure oleic acid in alcohol equivalent amount of sodium ethoxide was added when sodium oleate was precipitated. The precipitate was filtered, recrystallised from alcohol, finally washed with dried ether and kept in a vacuum desiccator. It was later found that instead of purifying oleic acid through barium salt, the same result could be obtained by distilling oleic acid twice or thrice under reduced pressure. Oleic acid in alcohol can be neutralised with alcoholic caustic soda instead of sodium ethoxide. The solution after neutralisation is evaporated on the water-bath and then taken in alcohol. Two or three recrystallisations from alcohol, followed by ether washing give practically a pure product of m.p. 228-29°. The myristic, lauric and capric acids and saponin were obtained from Eastman Kodak Company. The sodium salts of the three acids were prepared and purified in the same way as sodium oleate. Sodium stearate and palmitate have also been tried but they are sparingly soluble in water. An 1 or 0.5% solution can be prepared in hot water but on cooling it sets to a gel. Emulsions have been prepared in the usual way. Xylene was purified by fractional distillation and dried over fused CaCl_2 .

To ascertain the effect of the emulsifying agents, viscosity of xylene emulsions stabilised with sodium oleate, myristate, laurate, capriate and saponin were measured in a rotary viscometer at 30°. For each viscosity measurement 5 or 6 readings were taken by varying the rates of shear. In the following tables (I-V) the mean viscosity as well as the viscosities at the minimum and maximum rates of shear are given. (The

mean viscosity is taken as the average of 5 or 6 viscosities taken at different rates of shear). It is to be noted, however, that maximum viscosity is not necessarily obtained at the maximum rate of shear. The data are summarised in Table VI.

TABLE I

1% Sodium oleate-xylene system.

Vol. % of xylene.	Rate of shear.		Shearing stress $\times 100$.		η in c. p.			Yield value
	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Mean.	
10	4.62	30.04	28.3	131.0	3.95	4.03	3.97	0.1
20	16.64	43.91	118	309	6.49	6.81	6.71	0.1
30	12.48	28.65	141	299	10.5	10.09	10.17	0.1
40	16.64	34.20	260	528	14.42	14.85	14.66	0.2
50	11.55	22.64	239	453	18.05	19.13	19.07	0.2
60	12.48	35.98	360	10.9	27.28	26.74	26.99	0.2
80	7.85	14.79	1468	1914	65.98	65.24	65.40	9.5

TABLE II

1% Sodium myristate-xylene system.

Vol. % of xylene.	Rate of shear.		Shearing stress $\times 100$.		η in c.p.			Yield value.
	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Mean.	
10	22.18	32.35	113.3	150.6	4.66	4.62	4.63	0.1
20	13.86	26.80	105.6	188.0	6.90	6.54	6.74	0.1
30	13.86	30.04	170	355.0	11.54	11.48	11.50	0.1
40	9.70	26.80	159.6	401.7	14.39	14.24	14.28	0.2
50	16.64	27.73	340	551	19.23	19.52	19.28	0.2
70	6.47	20.11	448	978	38.33	38.69	38.41	2.0

TABLE III

1% Sodium laurate-xylene system.

Vol. % of xylene.	Rate of shear.		Shearing stress $\times 100$.		η in c.p.			Yield value
	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Mean.	
10	12.02	36.51	41.19	100.4	2.59	2.48	2.52	0.1
40	12.48	25.43	152.0	283.0	10.58	10.35	10.44	0.2
50	9.70	16.17	182.8	291.0	16.90	16.77	16.78	0.2
60	9.24	30.04	239.5	739.7	23.74	23.95	23.74	0.2
80	11.55	19.41	997.4	1517.0	64.42	65.28	64.74	2.5

TABLE IV

2% Sodium capriate-xylene system.

Vol. % of xylene.	Rate of shear.		Shearing stress $\times 100$.		η in c.p.			Yield value.
	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Mean.	
10	19.87	39.75	59.2	105.5	2.48	2.40	2.45	0.1
20	23.11	37.43	131.3	213.7	5.25	5.44	5.33	0.1
30	16.64	33.74	154.0	291.0	8.68	8.33	8.51	0.1
40	8.32	23.57	175.9	301.3	11.53	11.90	11.71	0.2
50	11.55	26.80	195.6	433.7	15.20	15.59	15.38	0.2
60	11.55	23.80	296.1	597.4	23.91	24.26	24.06	0.2

TABLE V

2% Saponin - xylene system.

Vol. % of xylene.	Rate of shear.		Shearing stress $\times 100$.		η in c.p.			Yield value
	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Mean.	
10	9.24	47.14	114.0	438.0	9.09	8.66	8.82	0.03
20	12.01	26.57	306.0	644.0	22.13	22.69	22.59	0.4
30	18.95	35.59	842.0	1488.0	40.21	39.56	39.73	0.8
40	10.63	30.04	762.0	1936.0	62.32	61.20	61.60	1.0
50	11.09	30.50	1100.0	2863.0	88.39	89.95	88.78	1.2
60	3.69	18.49	932.0	3476.0	171.3	171.8	171.4	3.0

TABLE VI

Viscosity of xylene emulsions stabilised with different emulsifiers.

Vol. % of xylene.	1% Na oleate. (0.033 N).	1% Na myristate. (0.04 N).	1% Na laurate (0.05 N).	2% Na capriate (0.103 N).	0.5% Saponin
10	3.57(0.10)	4.63(0.10)	2.52(0.10)	2.45(0.10)	8.82(0.30)
20	6.71(0.10)	6.74(0.10)	...	5.33(0.10)	22.59(0.40)
30	10.37(0.10)	11.50(0.10)	...	8.51(0.10)	39.73(0.80)
40	14.65(0.20)	14.28(0.20)	10.54(0.20)	11.71(0.20)	61.60(1.0)
50	10.07(0.20)	19.28(0.20)	16.78(0.20)	15.38(0.20)	88.78(1.2)
60	26.99(0.20)	...	23.74(0.20)	24.06(0.20)	171.4(3.0)
70	39.27(4.0)	38.41(2.0)	...	...	...
80	65.40(9.5)	...	64.74(2.5)	...	...

Figures within bracket indicate yield values.

TABLE VII

0.5% Saponin - paraffin oil system.

Vol. % of oil	Rate of shear.		Shearing stress $\times 100$.		η in c.p.			Yield values.
	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Mean.	
20	9.24	22.18	327.0	623.0	23.48	23.13	23.37	1.1
30	16.17	36.51	842.0	1643.0	39.68	39.53	39.57	2.0
40	9.24	23.11	832.0	1720.0	62.96	63.60	63.03	2.5

TABLE VIII

2% Saponin - paraffin oil system.

Vol. % of oil.	Rate of shear.		Shearing stress $\times 100$.		η in c.p.			Yield values.
	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Mean.	
20	13.30	32.35	463.0	974.0	23.36	23.61	23.43	1.5
30	9.24	25.43	595.0	1256.0	39.49	40.34	39.97	2.3
40	4.62	18.49	538.0	1430.0	62.34	63.83	63.21	2.5

TABLE IX

Vol. % of oil.	η with 0.5% saponin.	η with 2% saponin.
20	23.37	23.43
30	39.57	39.97
40	63.03	63.21

It will be noted from the data recorded in Table VI that the viscosity of emulsions depends a great deal on the nature of the emulsifier used. Saponin emulsions have viscosities greater than those of the soap-stabilised emulsions. Emulsions stabilised with laurate and capriate have viscosities slightly less than those of oleate and myristate. Another point of interest is, that barring saponin, the difference in the viscosities of the emulsions diminishes as the proportion of the dispersed phase is increased. As regards stabilising capacity it is found that sodium capriate is decidedly a much weaker emulsifier than the others. When the dispersed phase is 40 to 50% of the total volume, 1% capriate does not produce an emulsion, while the other soaps at the same concentration give a stable emulsion. After capriate, comes the laurate while for the other soaps and saponin, it is rather difficult to compare their emulsifying power. Emulsions with cetyl salts are least viscous, are formed practically spontaneously and are quite stable, thus the common view that the increase of viscosity increases the stability by hindering the coalescence of drops cannot be justified in this case.

The variation of viscosity with the nature of an emulsifier is rather difficult to explain, but it may be assumed that the interfacial film which stabilises the emulsion plays the vital role for this change in viscosity. The question may be raised that as we have considered the effect of soaps in terms of percentages and not in terms of molecular proportion, the results may not be strictly comparable. On careful analysis it will be found that this does not affect our conclusion. The concentrations of oleate and myristate used (1%) are respectively 0.033*N* and 0.04*N*, yet their viscosities are more or less the same. The normalities of laurate and capriate are 0.045 and 0.1031 but they do not affect the resulting viscosity. To establish this point beyond doubt, experiments were carried out using paraffin oil as the internal phase and saponin (2% and 0.5%) as the emulsifier. The data are recorded in Tables VII—VIII while Table IX gives the summarised results.

The data in Table IX show clearly that the viscosity of emulsions with widely varying concentrations of saponin is nearly the same. Hence, it can be inferred with a fair degree of accuracy that substitution of molar concentration in place of percentage concentration will not affect the conclusions already arrived at.

Referring to Table VI, it is observed that the yield values increase with the increase in the concentration of the dispersed phase. In most of the systems the yield values are rather small and do not change appreciably up to 60% of the dispersed phase. After this, it rises sharply with further increase in concentration of the internal phase.

Experimental Test of the various Viscosity Equations

Various viscosity equations have been discussed in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*). It is proposed to test further the applicability of these equations to the data recorded in this paper. Viscosity of soap solutions and saponin has been measured as usual in an Ostwald viscometer. The viscosities obtained in c. p. at 30° are sodium oleate (1%), 0.8482; sodium laurate (1%), 0.8435; saponin (0.5%), 0.8531; sodium capriate (2%), 0.8482.

Viscosity of sodium myristate at 30° cannot be measured as at this temperature gelation occurs. It has already been stated in the previous paper that Einstein's

and Hatschek's equations are not applicable to any one of the systems studied and the kind of deviation is illustrated with sodium oleate—xylene system in Table X.

$$\text{Sibree's equation} \quad \eta = \frac{\eta_0}{1 - \frac{1}{3} \sqrt{k \phi}}$$

$$\text{Richardson's simple equation} \quad \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = e^{-k\phi} \quad \text{and}$$

$$\text{Richardson's modified equation (cf. Neogy and Ghosh, } \textit{loc. cit.}) \quad \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = e^{-(k\phi + c)}$$

were also examined. It is found that only Richardson's modified equation can represent the results to an accuracy of 5%. The other two equations fail miserably. Tables XI—XIII illustrate this.

TABLE X

Sodium oleate—xylene system.
 ϕ represents phase volume ratio.

Vol. % of xylene.	Values calculated from		Observed values.
	Einstein's eqn. $\eta = \eta_0(1 + 2.5 \phi)$	Hatschek's eqn. $\eta = \frac{\eta_0}{1 - \frac{1}{3} \sqrt{\phi}}$	
10	1.060	1.584	3.97
20	1.273	2.043	6.71
30	1.485	2.565	10.37
40	1.696	3.223	14.66
50	1.908	4.113	19.07
60	2.120	5.420	26.99

TABLE XI

Sodium oleate—xylene system.

Vol % of xylene.	Observed values of $\log \eta/\eta_0$.	Calculated values of $\log \eta/\eta_0$ from		
		Sibree's equation $\eta = \eta_0 \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{3} \sqrt{1.3 \phi}}$	Richardson's equation ($K = 3.00$) †	Richardson's modified eqn. ($K = 1.7, c = 0.54$)
10	0.6703	0.3068	0.309	0.71
20	0.8982	0.4417	0.618	0.88
30	1.0872	0.5689	0.927	1.05
40	1.2377	0.7080	1.2377	1.22
50	1.3512	0.8735	1.545	1.39
60	1.5029	1.1002	1.854	1.56
70	1.6655	1.51	2.163	1.73
80	1.8871	...	2.472	1.90

TABLE XII

Sodium laurate-xylene system.

Vol. % of xylene,	Observed values of $\log \eta/\eta_0$.	Sibree's equation.	Calculated values of $\log \eta/\eta_0$ from	
			Richardson's equation ($K=2.742$)†	Richardson's modified eqn. ($K=2.0, c=0.28$).
10	0.4754	0.3068	0.2742	0.48
40	1.0959	0.7080	1.0969	1.08
50	1.2588	0.8735	1.3710	1.28
60	1.4494	1.1002	1.6452	1.48
80	1.8852	...	2.936	1.88

TABLE XIII

Saponin-xylene system.

Vol. % of xylene.	Observed values of $\log \eta/\eta_0$.	Sibree's equation.	Calculated values of $\log \eta/\eta_0$ from	
			Richardson's equation ($K=4.65$)†	Richardson's modified equation. ($K=2.23, c=0.96$).
10	1.0745	0.3068	0.465	1.183
20	1.4229	0.4417	0.930	1.406
30	1.6681	0.5689	1.395	1.629
40	1.8586	0.7080	1.8586	1.852
50	2.0173	0.8735	2.325	2.075
60	2.3113	1.1002	2.790	2.298

† The values of K in Richardson's original equation have always been calculated from 40% emulsion.

Fig. 1

Sibree's claim that his equation is applicable when the concentration of the dispersed phase exceeds 50%, does not seem to be justified. On plotting $\log \eta/\eta_0$ against ϕ a straight line is obtained (Fig. 1) but it does not pass through the origin in any case. This conclusively shows that Richardson's simple equation is not correct, but his modified equation is correct. The values of ' k ' and ' c ' as found from the plots are given in Tables XI—XIII.

The values of c varies with the soap used, thus it is 0.54, 0.28 and 0.96 for emulsions stabilised with sodium oleate, laurate and saponin respectively.